

Judul: Submission IJEEP-S-663-671

Tanggal: 2020-05-27 1:46

Pengirim: "Ilhan Ozturk" <ijEEP@econjournals.com>

Penerima: "Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Dear Dr. Achmad Faqih,

International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy has received of your submission, "THE INCREASING OF COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRO-INDUSTRY PRODUCTS THROUGH INSTITUTIONAL EMPOWERMENT TO SUPPORT THE ACHIEVEMENT OF SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT" (ref: IJEEP-S-663-671).

You may check the status of your submission by logging in as an author here:

<http://www.econjournals.com/index.php/ijEEP/index>.

With Best Wishes,

Ilhan Ozturk, Editor in Chief

Editor in Chief

International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy

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(Use the following URL: <http://www.econjournals.com/index.php/ijEEP/index>) Please contact the publication office if you have any questions

Judul: Your revision is past due (IJEPP-S-663-671)
Tanggal: 2020-06-17 5:42
Pengirim: "Ilhan Ozturk" <ijeep@econjournals.com>
Penerima: "Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Dear Dr. Achmad Faqih,

The revision of your submission IJEPP-S-663-671 was expected by June 30, 2020. If you require more time, please respond to this message. If your revision is ready, then please go to <http://www.econjournals.com/index.php/ijeep/index> and submit the revision.

With Best Wishes,
Ilhan Ozturk, Editor in Chief
Editor in Chief
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Judul: Author Notification of Production Tasks for (IJEOP-S-663-671)

Tanggal: 2020-07-30 10:52

Pengirim: "Ilhan Ozturk" <ijeop@econjournals.com>

Penerima: "Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Dear Dr. Achmad Faqih,

Your paper THE INCREASING OF COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRO-INDUSTRY PRODUCTS THROUGH INSTITUTIONAL EMPOWERMENT TO SUPPORT THE ACHIEVEMENT OF SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT, ref: IJEOP-S-663-671 was recently accepted by International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy.

We are now processing your paper for publication, and need you to log in using this link: Production Task Assignment which will take you to your Current Task Assignment where you will need to use the action link "Submit Task" to provide the following information:

- 1) Download, sign and upload the Copyright Assignment Form from <http://www.econjournals.com/index.php/ijeop/about/submissions#copyright> Notice options
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- 2) If you provided a PDF file of your paper during the peer review process, you will now need to upload a Word document of the text, tables and the original figure files. If your paper is in LaTeX format we will need the LaTeX files as well as the PDF.
- 3) If your figures are in colour, you will need to indicate whether you would like the figures to be printed in colour or black and white. If you would like the figures to be printed in colour, there is a charge of \$350 for each colour figure. If you would like the figures to be printed in black and white, please ensure there is no reference to the colour in the text or captions and that the figures can still be understood without colour. Note that colour figures are published online in colour at no charge. You can supply replacement figures if necessary.

You must complete this task within two days in order for the production process to proceed. If you have any questions regarding the task please respond to this message.

With Best Wishes,
Ilhan Ozturk, Editor in Chief
Editor in Chief
International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy
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Judul: Accepted Letter

Tanggal: 2020-08-04 11:06

Pengirim: "Ilhan Ozturk" <ijeep@econjournals.com>

Penerima: "Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Dear Dr. Achmad Faqih,

I am pleased to tell you that your submission "THE INCREASING OF COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRO-INDUSTRY PRODUCTS THROUGH INSTITUTIONAL EMPOWERMENT TO SUPPORT THE ACHIEVEMENT OF SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT" has been accepted for publication in International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy. It was accepted on August 04, 2020

You will hear from Econ Journals soon regarding the publication of your paper. Thank you for submitting your work to International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy.

With Best Wishes,
Ilhan Ozturk, Editor in Chief
Editor in Chief
International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy
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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENERGY ECONOMICS AND POLICY
ISSN: 2146-4553

Date: 5 May 2020
Ref.: 7749/IJEEP/2019

Dear Achmad Faqih¹, Roosganda Elizabeth², Delima Hasri Azahari³

It's my pleasure to inform you that, after the peer review, your paper, *The Increasing of Competitiveness of Agro-Industry Products through Institutional Empowerment to Support the Achievement of Sustainable Agricultural Development* been ACCEPTED to publish with **International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy**, ISSN: **2146-4553**. It will be published in the coming issue.

You will need to pay the publication fee as soon as possible. I believe that our collaboration will help to accelerate the global knowledge creation and sharing one step further. Please do not hesitate to contact me if you have any further questions.

Sincerely,

Alihan OZTURK

Editor

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